

The Effect Of The Flipped Classroom Strategy On Developing Scientific Literacy And Decision-Making Skills Among Students Of The Chemical And Physical Concepts Course

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Article Info	Abstract
<p data-bbox="199 504 368 530">Article History</p> <p data-bbox="199 562 360 622">Received: April 29, 2021</p> <p data-bbox="199 654 352 714">Accepted: July 30, 2021</p> <hr/> <p data-bbox="199 745 328 772">Keywords :</p> <p data-bbox="199 777 469 987">Flipped Classroom, Scientific Literacy, Acquiring Chemical Concepts, Scientific Thinking, And Attitudes Towards Science Decision-Making Skills</p> <p data-bbox="199 1019 264 1046">DOI:</p> <p data-bbox="199 1050 480 1077">10.5281/zenodo.5148818</p>	<p data-bbox="560 504 1394 1108"><i>This study aimed to identify the impact of the flipped classroom strategy on developing Scientific Literacy and decision-making skills among classroom teacher students. The study sample consisted of 62 students of the Bachelor of Classroom Teacher at the University of Islamic Sciences 2020/2021, divided into an experimental group, and a control group. To achieve the objectives of the study, a teacher's guide was prepared according to the flipped classroom strategy, the chemical concepts test, the attitudes toward science scale, the scientific thinking test, and the decision-making scale, and the validity and stability of the study tools were verified. To answer the study questions, the arithmetic means and standard deviations of the two groups were calculated, and the accompanying analysis of variance ANCOVA was used to test the significance of differences in the arithmetic means of students in the experimental and control groups. The results showed the effectiveness of the flipped classroom strategy in developing Scientific Literacy (acquiring chemical concepts, scientific thinking, and attitudes towards science) and decision-making skills among the classroom teacher students, and the presence of a statistically significant difference at a level of $\alpha = 0.05$ between the average performance of the study sample students in the experimental and control groups, attributed to the flipped classroom strategy for the students of the experimental group.</i></p>

Introduction

Current developments have posed a great challenge for various educational institutions in preparing their programs to suit the learners who can adapt to these changes, provide them with the appropriate facts and knowledge, develop their skills to obtain knowledge from its source, provide them with scientific thinking skills to solve their daily problems. The program should also develop learners' attitudes towards science to understand the evolving world of practice and its role in Community Service. Education is considered a crucial developmental process for any country that seeks to develop (Mackatiani et al., 2016). Science takes a distinguished position among the study subjects because it deals with natural phenomena and the laws governing them, working to integrate their applications in various areas of life. Thus, science education acquires importance in all countries striving for development (Schulze & Lemmer, 2017).

Learning science encourages students to deal properly with scientific ideas, enhances their imagination abilities, and increases their motivation towards science and learning. The concept of enlightenment has gained importance, in both developing and developed countries. In the 1960s, scientific literacy (S.L.) became a major goal in the teaching of science, as preparing citizens for fruitful participation in the life of society became incomplete without Scientific Literacy. Definitions of the term Scientific Literacy varied. Paul De Hurd (1958) used the concept of enlightenment, which he described as "the understanding of science and its applications in society". The term "scientific literacy" was introduced at the end of the 1950s by Hurd, (1958) who defined it as "making a decision that includes responsibility for science and technology, and the possession of the knowledge and intellectual skills of the cognitive movement". In 1963, Robert Carlton prepared his survey study on defining the concept, which was published in the *Journal of the National Science Teachers Association* (NSTA). He concluded that the scientific educators' concept of the term Scientific Literacy was represented in the topics related to science and society at that time. In 1967, Milton Pella asked a hundred educators a question about the meaning of scientific enlightenment, and their answers included the relationship between science and society, science, and technology, understanding the nature of science, ethics of science, and the role of science in human life. In the 1970s, within the framework of school science education for the decade of the seventies, the National Science Teachers Association (NSTA) identified the goal of science education in preparing the scientifically enlightened individual. Knowledge regarding various sciences like physics, biology, and earth sciences, have been categorized into facts, concepts, and theories. The second aspect is related to the individual's proper behavior towards everyday life situations and the associated trends and skills.

Scientific Literacy was defined by the American Association for the Advancement of Science in 1989 and 1993, as “the inclusion of knowledge and understanding of the basic concepts of science, mathematics, technology, and methods of scientific thinking that enable an individual to use this knowledge and these methods on a personal and social level; the manifestations of enlightenment are defined by knowledge of the natural world and respect for its unity, familiarity with some basic knowledge of science, and the ability to use scientific thinking methods and the use of scientific knowledge”.

Scientific concepts are very important, as educators have been interested in their development by formulating various strategies, methods, and teaching methods (Abed, 2016; Hamadneh, 2017; Okedeyi et al., 2015).

Concepts are mental representations that allow us to conclude about the things we encounter in our daily lives (Murphy, 2002). Scientific concepts are important in that they reduce the complexity of the environment, which is the language of science and the key to knowledge, help in solving problems in daily life situations, and strengthen the ability to make decisions (Awad-Allah, 2012). Learning scientific concepts increases the effectiveness of learning; it contributes to the students' ability to use the knowledge they possess, to adapt it to generate new knowledge, and to apply it in thinking and solving problems.

Scientific Literacy and decision-making ability are basic skills that should be developed by university students so that they can collect information related to scientific concepts, use it effectively in their scientific thinking skills and participate effectively in making decisions that confront them. Therefore, there is a need to adopt a teaching strategy to keep pace with scientific and technological development and develop the Scientific Literacy of student teachers and their decision-making ability. One of the most important subjects in which we need to raise the level of education is science in all its forms-- biological, physical, chemical, and others-- to keep pace with technological development, and to adapt to the requirements of the current era. Employing the Internet in the educational process as a technological tool is an urgent necessity, because of its many features and various applications. The flipped class is an important strategy in the educational field, as it helps the learner to research and investigate and encourages him to make the appropriate decision. The flipped row to Jonathen Bergmam and Sam Arson, concerned that students will miss classes by participating in competitions and festivals in remote areas that require travel. This forced them to record lectures and lessons using live videos and publish them on YouTube so that students can access the scientific material easily (Hamdan et al, 2013; Johnson et al., 2014). The flipped classroom is one of the strategies that are in line with modern education trends, especially in these times of educational trends dictated by the Corona pandemic Studies (Al Hosania, 2015; Schoolwires Network, 2012) indicate that the student has become a researcher and an effective user of technology through self-learning and scientific thinking (Johnson et al., 2014) It also indicates that flipped learning is one of the blended learning styles that combines the activation of technology in learning. The flipped learning strategy works on enriching the educational process and achieving positive learning outcomes at the cognitive level represented by increasing achievement, acquisition of skills, and at the emotional level, represented by the love of the study material and positive interaction with it. Hence, this study aims to understand the effect of the inverted class on developing Scientific Literacy and decision-making skills in a chemical concepts course.

Study problem and questions

Through educational experience, the researcher noticed a weakness in Scientific Literacy, viz., the chemical concepts of the classroom teacher students and their negative attitudes towards scientific concepts, in addition to their weakness in dealing with scientific concepts in their daily lives and the inability to make decisions. The teachers of science subjects in schools face significant difficulties in teaching chemical concepts for the first grades. Through the teacher's feedback, a perceptible weakness was found in students, while dealing with scientific issues and problems. Therefore, the study problem stemmed from the low level of Scientific Literacy among the classroom teacher students, and the globally realized importance of scientific literacy as a standard for high and low-quality education, especially through the Program for International Student Assessment (PISA) made up of highly industrialized countries (OECD).

Technological tools such as the Internet have provided teachers with the opportunity to develop new educational strategies on the educational stage, which, in the researcher's opinion, have a strong relationship with improving the trend towards learning science, especially chemistry, in respect of questions and activities that require scientific thinking skills and then making decisions about them. As flipped learning builds the student's personality, it is better to continue from the lower basic stage until it grows with students at all stages of their lives (, 2016). Therefore, the classroom teacher students must be trained in flipped learning before they join the service, considering the foregoing, and the importance of the subject. The researcher decided to try to identify the impact of the flipped classroom strategy on Scientific Literacy and decision-making skills among the classroom teacher students of chemistry. Accordingly, the study problem is summarized in answering the main question:

- What is the effectiveness of an interactive learning environment through a flipped class-based e-learning platform in developing Scientific Literacy in students of a chemical and physical concepts course? The main question stems from the following sub-questions:

1. Does the degree of acquiring chemical concepts differ with a statistical significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$) among female classroom teacher students according to the teaching strategy used (flipped class/traditional class)?

2. Does the degree of developing scientific thinking skills differ statistically at the significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$) among female classroom teacher students according to the teaching strategy used (flipped class/traditional class)?

3. Does the degree of developing an attitude towards science differ with a statistical significance at the level ($\alpha = 0.05$) among female classroom teacher students according to the teaching strategy used (flipped class/traditional class)?

4. Does the degree of decision-making differ at the statistical significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$) among female classroom teacher students according to the teaching strategy used (flipped class/traditional class)?

Study importance

The importance of this study stems from two aspects: the first is theoretical importance, through which it will add a sufficient theoretical background to the flipped classroom strategy and its impact on Scientific Literacy and decision-making among classroom teacher students, and its presentation of a distinguished educational scientific strategy that contributes to raising the knowledge level of university students. Additionally, this is among the first local studies that seek to identify the impact of the inverted class strategy on Scientific Literacy and decision-making during the Corona pandemic, as the researcher did not find any research or local or Arab studies that dealt with this aspect, as far as the researcher's knowledge goes.

Practical importance:

The importance of this study is its contribution in directing those responsible for the development of higher education in the provision of academic programs and design of educational videos on Scientific Literacy and decision-making among students of higher education, during a period of crises such as the Corona pandemic. The application of this strategy can enhance the process of developing modern tools for science teaching and overcome the challenges facing students and teachers. It may help the bachelor's degree teachers to follow modern teaching methods in scientific subjects and address the physical absence of students. This study opens new horizons for researchers in the educational field to follow up on this study.

Study limits

1. Spatial limits: This study was limited to BA student (62) classroom teachers enrolled in a chemical concepts course at the University of Islamic Sciences.

2. Temporal limits: The study was limited to the first semester of the year (2020-2021).

3. Objective limits: The study was limited to measuring the effect of the flipped classroom strategy for teaching chemical concepts in developing Scientific Literacy and decision-making skill among classroom teacher students.

Procedural concepts

Flipped classroom is an educational method based on exposing students to new knowledge outside the classroom by watching recorded lessons and the process of discussion, dialogue, and problem-solving in the classroom (Brame, 2013). It is procedurally defined as presenting the scientific material and homework of a chemical concepts course to the classroom teacher students by watching videos related to chemical concepts, followed by practice activities, exercises, and discussion in a lecture through the Microsoft Teams platform, with the lecture time devoted to discussions and exercises.

Scientific Literacy: Toharudin et al. (2011) define Scientific Literacy as the ability to understand written and oral science and scientific communication, and the ability to solve problems, so that students have a high sensitivity towards themselves and the environment to make sound scientific decisions. It is procedurally defined as the students' familiarity with a certain amount of knowledge, chemical concepts, and scientific thinking skills, their acquisition of positive attitudes towards science, employing them in understanding the phenomena, events, and scientific problems facing them, and actively contributing to their solution. It is measured procedurally in this study through the test of scientific concepts, the test of scientific thinking, and the measure of attitude towards science.

Chemical concepts This term refers to the meaning, understanding, and application of the concepts contained in a chemical concepts course, measured procedurally by the student's acquisition of chemical concepts, represented by the score that the students obtain in the chemical concepts test.

Attitudes toward science refers to the group of classroom teacher students' responses comprised of acceptance, rejection, or neutrality toward accepting the nature and learning of science and feeling its

importance. It is measured procedurally by the score that the student obtains on the scale of attitude toward science, prepared in this study.

Scientific thinking is “a set of integrated mental skills necessary to solve a problem facing a person in his daily or scientific life using a scientific approach that has objectivity and is accurate and consists of the following skills: defining the problem, choosing appropriate hypotheses, choosing the validity of the hypothesis, interpreting data, and generalizing” (Al-Qadri, 2012).

Procedurally, the scientific thinking skills were measured by the score that the students obtained on the scientific thinking skills scale.

Decision-making Skill: “The individual collects the most accurate information, experiences, and performance that confirm and enhance his choice of one of the alternatives and reduce the importance and attractiveness of the rejected alternative, thus reducing the conflict situation that results from the cognitive dissonance that includes decision-making” (Festinger, 1962, p.23). It is procedurally defined as affording students the ability to identify the problem, compare and choose between a set of alternatives, and choose and evaluate the best solutions, to achieve a goal or positive results during the study of the atomic structure in chemistry. It is measured by the score that the student obtains in decision-making skills scale.

Theoretical Framework and Previous Studies

Active learning and self-learning are two main keys to the flipped classroom strategy, and they affect the learning environment primarily by moving from the centralization of learning from the teacher to the student so that the student becomes a producer of knowledge that has no future, as well as the cognitive and constructivist learning theories that form a cornerstone in building this strategy (Aronson et al., 2013).

Vygotsky's theory (development of the central area) is also one of the most important theories on which the flipped classroom strategy is focused. Vygotsky believes that learners can learn autonomously when exposed to a new experience in the central area in their brain, and only need guidance and supervision by the teacher to modify its course, and to reach mastery (Al-Ruwais, 2016).

The application of flipped learning dates to 1998, when Johnson and Walvoord (1998) encouraged its use by allowing students to view educational content at home, and dedicating class time to the processes of discussion, analysis, synthesis, and problem-solving. The flipped class - or flipped learning - is the heart of the learning tasks between the classroom and the home, so that the teacher exploits technology to prepare the lesson, through a videotape of no more than ten minutes, or a video file using audio-visual techniques and simulation programs, to be perused by the student at home. This is followed by the class activities and solving of the practical problems from the homework in the class. This enhances the students' understanding of the material, which is accessible to them before the lesson and throughout. The *modus operandi* of a flipped classroom is this: the teacher prepares a video to watch the lesson outside the classroom and uses the class time in the flipped classroom for work, activities, experiments, teamwork, and evaluation of work progress (Aronson & Arfstrom, 2013).

Bergman and Sams (2012) indicate that the benefit of flipped learning lies in helping students with low achievement, who receive assistance from the teacher who wanders among the students, helping them to acquire and comprehend concepts. Students watching educational videos at home enables the teacher to segregate those who need more time to learn and direct them towards improving their performance. The flipped classroom strategy is only one of the types of blended learning that use technology to transfer lessons outside the classroom. It is thus a part of a wide movement in which blended learning intersects, learning by inquiry and other teaching strategies that seek flexibility, activate the role of the student, and make learning enjoyable and interesting. This enables students to benefit from self-learning and use the time in the classroom to perform activities and assignments. For the flipped classroom strategy to be applied effectively and efficiently, the following are the key elements:

- Flexible learning: The teacher can rearrange the learning environment in proportion to the educational situation on the one hand and with the level of students and the possibility of learning at any time, on the other.
- Learning culture involves making the student the center of the educational learning process so that he can form knowledge effectively and positively.
- Specific content refers to the teacher specifying what the student should see outside the classroom.
- A professional Teacher is one who can employ technology within the technological process (Nagal, 2013).
- Learning with the flipped classroom strategy has many educational benefits and advantages, the most important of which are as follows (Butt, 2013; Brame, 2010; Millard, 2010):
- A good investment of classroom time and building a strong relationship between the student and the teacher through communication via social networking sites,
- Improving students' achievement, developing their mental processes, and encouraging the optimal use of educational technology

- Allowing students to first view the content, and to prepare before the time of the lesson in any place and at the time of their choice, according to the speed of their learning.
- Providing a mechanism for assessing students' comprehension.

Through the application of the flipped classroom strategy through the Microsoft Teams platform, the new information reaches the student at home, working within the lower levels of Bloom's cognitive pyramid (remembering, understanding, and application). Thereafter, the teacher and student work together to develop the higher skills of the pyramid (analysis, evaluation, and innovation) through classroom activities and exercises. In the traditional classroom, the focus is on providing information on the lower levels of the pyramid, while the student cannot apply what he has learned within the higher levels of Bloom. Gopalan (2018) aimed to determine the conditions of the activities that will be discussed in the classroom through flipped learning, with a study sample of 120 male and female teachers studying in schools that follow the flipped learning system in the state of Illinois. A questionnaire was distributed to the sample, and through appropriate analysis tools, the study concluded that the most important condition that must be met in flipped learning activities is that the questionnaire should be open-ended, with multiple correct options. Al-Rusa (2017) aimed to identify the effectiveness of the flipped classroom in teaching, evaluate the science teaching strategies course on academic achievement and develop the habits of mind among students of Princess Nourah bint Abdulrahman University. To verify the research questions and hypotheses, the researcher used the experimental method. The research sample consisted of 54 female students from the Department of Curricula and Teaching Methods at Noura bint Abdul Rahman University in Saudi Arabia. They were divided into an experimental group consisting of 27 students who studied the course using the flipped classroom, and a control group consisting of 27 female students who traditionally studied the course. The research tools consisted of a test of academic achievement and a measure of habits of mind that were applied to the experimental and control groups. The results indicated that there were statistically significant differences between the averages of the experimental group and the control group, in favor of the experimental group. Sinouvassane and Nalini (2016) aimed to compare the use of the flipped learning strategy between 24 first-year and third-year students in the Bachelor of Health Sciences in India, with 51 students in the first year, and 27 in the third year. The flipped learning strategy was employed in both groups of students by the same faculty member. After the experiment, a questionnaire was given to the students to obtain their observations and perceptions about the use of the flipped learning strategy in teaching. The results showed the effectiveness of using this strategy for learning basic concepts, by displaying the published study materials and videos before the lecture, which gave the faculty member more space to focus on the most important part during the lecture. Further, the students found that the strategy helped them acquire problem-solving skills and led to increased student participation in discussions in the lecture hall during the learning process.

All studies so far relating to the flipped class strategy covered school stages, and according to the researcher's knowledge, there are no studies related to university students in Jordan, and no studies showing the impact of this flipped class on the development of Scientific Literacy and decision-making, and no studies within the Arab or Jordanian environment. This is what distinguishes this study from previous studies. Hence, this study came to investigate the effectiveness of an interactive learning environment via an e-learning platform based on the flipped classroom in developing cognitive enlightenment and decision-making skills in students of a chemical and physical concepts course.

Method and Procedures

The Study Sample

The sample of the study consisted of two groups of 62 students of chemical and physical concepts course at the University of Islamic Sciences, with an experimental group of 17 students who studied according to the flipped class strategy through the Timmys platform and a control group of 45 who studied according to the traditional classroom via the Microsoft Teams platform.

Study Tools

To achieve the objectives of the study and carry out its procedures, the researcher prepared the following study tools:

1. Chemical concepts test.
2. Scale of attitudes towards science.
3. Scientific thinking test.
4. Decision-making scale.

To answer the study questions and test the hypotheses, the following tools were prepared:

First: Chemical Concepts Test was built for a chemical concepts course, and was prepared in the light of the following steps:

Determine the objective of the test: The objective of the test is to measure the level of acquisition by the classroom teacher students of the chemical concepts included in the course description. The test items were formulated in their initial form and numbered (000) items in the style of multiple-choice questions.

Test validity: Considering the foregoing, the test was prepared in its initial form to include 34 items and presented to a group of specialized arbitrators to ascertain their views on the appropriateness of the test items, the representation of the test items for the objectives to be measured, the test items' coverage of the content, and the accuracy of the test. The paragraphs of the test were scientifically and linguistically sound. The arbitrators indicated that some paragraphs needed to be canceled, some paragraphs modified, and some paragraphs reformulated for better clarity. The opinions of the arbitrators were considered and the necessary amendments made.

The exploratory experimentation of the test: The test was administered to a survey sample from outside the study members consisting of 34 students from the classroom teacher students. This was done to calculate the test time, calculate the difficulty and discrimination coefficients for its paragraphs. The values of the difficulty coefficient for the test paragraphs ranged between 0.43 and 0.84, making the difficulty level acceptable. That is, it could distinguish between different categories of students, and this was confirmed by the values of the discrimination coefficient, which ranged between 0.60 and 0.21, acceptable for this study.

The stability of the test was verified by re-applying the test to the same exploratory sample, which is the classroom teacher students, two weeks after applying the test for the first time, and the correlation coefficient was calculated between the results of the students at both times, at (0.84) which is a coefficient of stability suitable for this study.

Attitudes towards Science Scale: After reviewing some of the literature and previous studies related to preparing the Attitudes Towards Science Scale, the researcher developed this scale according to the three-point Likert scale in its initial form, consisting of 29 paragraphs.

The validity of the attitudes towards science scale

To verify the validity of the scale, it was presented to a group of arbitrators, and as per their opinions, five paragraphs were deleted from the various fields, reducing the number of paragraphs of the scale in its final form to 24 items, distributed as follows.

Table (1) Items number of attitudes towards Science

Paragraph numbers	Direction dimensions
8-1	The importance of science
9-17	Interest in and enjoyment of science
24-18	Appreciating the efforts of teachers and scientists

The Stability Scale of Attitudes towards Science

To verify the stability of the scale, it was applied to an exploratory sample from outside the study sample, which consisted of 34 male and female students, and the reliability coefficient of Cronbach's alpha was calculated. The tool has become applicable.

Scientific Thinking Test

To verify the validity of the scientific thinking skills test, it was presented before its initial application to a group of 12 specialized arbitrators, for their observations about the language and the appropriateness of the test paragraphs to the level of students.

Test Stability

To verify the stability of the tool, the internal consistency was calculated on an exploratory sample from outside the study sample of 34 students.

From the initial experiment of the test on the sample, the researcher aimed to ascertain the clarity of the paragraphs for the students, their way of response, and to determine the time needed to complete the test. The reliability coefficient was calculated by Pearson correlation coefficient between the students' scores in the test, yielding a reliability coefficient of 0.91.

The stability of the test was also calculated by the method of internal consistency using Cronbach's alpha coefficient, which was found to be 0.71. These values are sufficient and appropriate for the study.

Results

To answer the main question: What is the effectiveness of an interactive learning environment via an e-learning platform based on the flipped classroom in developing Scientific Literacy for students of a chemical and physical concepts course? The main question includes the following sub-questions:

• **The first question: Does the degree of acquiring chemical concepts differ with a statistically significant level of $\alpha = 0.05$ among the female classroom teacher students according to the teaching strategy used (flipped class/ traditional class)?**

The arithmetical means and standard deviations were calculated for the achievement of the two study groups on the post-test acquisition of chemical concepts and their pre-test, according to the teaching strategy (the flipped class/ the traditional classroom), as per the following table: **Table (2)**

Means and standard deviations of the groups' performance in the chemical concepts acquisition test (methods of teaching)

Group	N	Pre-test		Post-test	
		M	Std	M	Std
Experimental	17	6.76	2.46	17.18	1.38
Control	45	5.24	1.99	6.73	2.32
Total	62	5.66	2.22	9.60	5.14

Table (2) shows an apparent difference between the averages of the two study groups on the post-test of acquisition of chemical concepts. The experimental group that studied using the flipped class strategy yielded an arithmetic mean of 16.29, while that of the control group that studied traditionally was 9.83. To ensure that the difference between the mean of the two study groups is statistically significant, at the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$), the accompanying one-way analysis of variance (ANCOVA) was applied, and the following table shows the results:

Table (3)
ANCOVA of the two groups' performance in the scientific concepts acquisition test (Method of teaching).

Source of variance	Sum of seq	Fd	Means of seq	F	Sig	² η
Pre-test	70.829	1	70.829	21.273	0.000	
Method of teaching	1043.298	1	1043.298	313.348	0.000	0.842
Error	196.442	59	3.33			
Adjusted total	1612.919	61				

Table (3) shows the value of (F) calculated for the difference in the achievement of the two study groups in the post-test acquisition of chemical concepts according to the teaching strategy at 313.348, which are significant values at a level of 0.000, thus ensuring that the difference between the two study groups in the acquisition test on post-chemical concepts, according to the teaching strategy, were statistically significant. For recognizing the difference in indications in favor of any of the two groups, modified arithmetic means, and standard errors were extracted for the achievement of the two study groups; Table (4) indicates that difference.

Table (4):
Adjusted mean and the standard error of the two groups'

performance in the chemical concepts acquisition test (method of teaching)

Standard error	Adjusted mean	N	Group
0.46	16.61	17	Experimental
0.28	6.95	45	Control

Table (4) shows that the experimental group studying through the flipped class strategy had an average arithmetic mean of 16.61, while that of the control group that studied traditionally, was 6.95. This indicates that the difference was in favor of the average of the experimental group *vis-à-vis* the average of the control group and confirms the effectiveness of an educational environment based on the flipped classroom strategy in the acquisition of chemical concepts by the classroom teacher's students. (0.842), and this shows that (84.2%) of the difference in the acquisition of chemical concepts is due to the flipped classroom teaching strategy, and the remaining percentage of the difference (15.8%) is due to other variables that the current study did not address.

Does the degree of developing scientific thinking skills differ with a statistical significance at the significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$ among female classroom teacher students according to the teaching strategy used (the flipped class/ the traditional class)?

To answer the second question of the study, the means, and standard deviations of the two study groups' achievement in the post-scientific thinking skills test and their pre-test were calculated according to the teaching strategy (flipped class/ traditional class), as reflected in the following table.

Table (5)

Means and standard deviations of the achievement of the two study groups in the post-scientific thinking skills test and their pre-test, according to the teaching strategy.

Group	N	Pre-test		Post-test	
		M	Std	M	Std
Experimental	17	7.47	2.48	16.53	1.77
Control	45	6.51	2.27	9.84	2.26
Total	62	6.77	2.35	11.68	3.68

Table (5) shows an apparent difference between the averages of the two study groups in the dimensional scientific thinking skills test. The experimental group, which studied using the flipped class strategy, obtained an arithmetic mean of 16.53, while that of the control group, which studied traditionally, was 9.84. To ensure that the difference between the mean of the two study groups is statistically significant, at the level of significance of $\alpha = 0.05$, the accompanying one-way analysis of variance (ANCOVA) was applied, and the following table shows the results:

Table (6)

ANCOVA results of the groups' performance in the test of scientific thinking skills, according to the teaching strategy.

Source of variance	Sum of seq	Fd	Means of seq	F	Sig.	η^2
Pre-test	2.888	1	2.888	0.628	0.431	
Method of teaching	547.311	1	547.311	119.043	0.000	0.669
Error	271.259	59	4.598			
Adjusted total	825.548	61				

Table (6) shows the value of F calculated for the difference in the achievement of the two study groups in the post-scientific thinking skills test according to the teaching strategy, at 119.043, which is significant at the level 0.000, thus ensuring that the difference between the two study groups in the dimensional scientific thinking test, according to the teaching strategy is statistically significant, and for identifying the difference in favor of any of the two groups, modified arithmetic mean and standard error were extracted for the achievement of the two study groups, and Table (7) indicates that difference.

Table (7)
Adjusted mean and standard error of the groups' performance in the test of scientific thinking skills according to the teaching strategy.

Group	N	Adjusted mean	Standard error
Experimental	17	16.60	0.53
Control	45	9.82	0.32

Table (7) shows that the experimental group taught using the flipped class strategy had average arithmetic mean of 16.60, while that of the control group taught by the traditional method was 9.82. This indicates that the difference was in favor of the average of the experimental group compared to that of the control group. This confirms the effectiveness of an educational environment based on the flipped classroom strategy in developing the scientific thinking skills of the classroom teacher students. This also confirms that the Eta squared value, which expresses the size of the impact this strategy had on developing scientific thinking skills, is 0.669, reflecting that 66.9% of the difference in developing scientific thinking skills is due to the flipped classroom teaching strategy, while the balance percentage of 33.1% is due to other variables that the current study did not address.

• Does the degree of developing the attitude towards science differ with a statistical significance at the level of $\alpha = 0.05$ among female classroom teacher students according to the teaching strategy used (flipped classroom/ traditional classroom)?

To answer the third question of the study, the arithmetical means and standard deviations were calculated for the achievement of the two study groups in the scale of attitude toward science pre- and post-test, according to the teaching strategy (flipped class/ traditional class), as shown in the following table.

Table (8)

Means and standard deviation of the students' performance in the scale of attitude towards Science.

Group	N	Pre-test	Post-test

		M	Std	M	Std
Experimental	17	26.65	2.00	54.53	5.93
Control	45	29.00	3.41	32.27	4.98
Total	62	28.35	3.25	38.37	11.29

Table 8 shows an apparent difference between the averages of the two study groups in the measure of attitude towards science. The experimental group that studied using the flipped class strategy obtained an arithmetic mean of 54.53, while the control group that studied traditionally obtained an arithmetic mean of 32.27. To ensure that the difference between the mean of the two study groups is statistically significant, at the level of $\alpha = 0.05$, the accompanying one-way analysis of variance (ANCOVA) was applied, as shown in the following table.

Table (9)
ANCOVA analysis of the groups' performance in the scale of attitude towards Science

Source of variance	Sum of seq	Fd	Means of seq	F	Sig.	η^2
Pre	356.616	1	356.616	16.23	0.000	
Method of teaching	6414.129	1	6414.129	291.907	0.000	0.832
Error	1296.419	59	21.973			
Adjusted total	7768.468	61				

Table (9) shows the calculated value of (F) for the difference in the achievement of the two study groups in the attitude scale toward dimensional science according to the teaching strategy equal to 291.907, which is significant at a level of 0.000, ensuring that the difference between the two study groups on the attitude scale towards dimensional science, according to the teaching strategy with a statistical significance, and to identify that the difference in favor of any of the two groups, the modified arithmetic mean and standard error were extracted for the achievement of the two study groups, as shown in Table (10).

Table (10)
Adjusted means and standard errors of the groups' performance in the scale of attitudes towards Science (teaching method)

Group	N	Adjusted mean	Standard error
Experimental	17	55.87	1.19
Control	45	31.76	0.71

Table (10) shows that the experimental group taught using the flipped class strategy got an arithmetic mean of 55.87, while that of the control group taught by the traditional method was 31.76. This indicates that the difference was in favor of the mean of the experimental group compared with the average of the control group. This confirms the effectiveness of an educational environment based on the flipped classroom strategy in the measure of attitude toward science among female classroom teacher students, and also confirms that the value of Eta squared, which expresses the size of the effect that this strategy had on the measure of attitude toward science, is 0.832.,

This shows that 83.2% of the difference in the attitude toward the science scale is due to the flipped classroom teaching strategy, while the rest of the difference (16.8%) is due to other variables that the current study did not address.

• Does the degree of decision-making differ with a statistical significance at the level of $\alpha = 0.05$ among the female classroom teacher students according to the teaching strategy used (flipped classroom/traditional classroom)?

To answer the fourth question of the study, the arithmetic means, and standard deviations were calculated for the achievement of the two study groups in the post-decision-making scale and their pre-test, according to the teaching strategy (flipped class/ the traditional classroom), as shown in the following table.

Table (11)

Means and standard deviations of the groups' performance in the decision-making scale (teaching method).

Group	N	Pre-test		Post-test	
		M	Std.	M	Std.
Experimental	17	42.88	6.25	70.35	9.91
Control	45	36.27	5.01	47.89	11.64
Total	62	38.08	6.10	54.05	15.02

Table (11) shows an apparent difference between the averages of the two study groups on the dimensional decision-making scale. The experimental group, which studied using the flipped class strategy, obtained an arithmetic mean of 70.35, while the control group, which studied traditionally, obtained a mean of 47.89. To ensure that the difference between the mean of the two study groups is statistically significant at the level of $\alpha = 0.05$, the accompanying one-way analysis of variance (ANCOVA) was applied, as reflected in the following table.

Table (12)
ANCOVA of the two groups' performance in the decision-making scale (Teaching strategy).

Source of variance	Sum of seq	Fd	Means of seq	F	Sig	² η
Pre-test	1036.093	1	1036.093	9.407	0.003	
Method of teaching	2829.252	1	2829.252	25.688	0.000	0.303
Error	6498.234	59	110.14			
Adjusted total	13760.855	61				

Table (12) shows the value of F calculated for the difference in the achievement of the two study groups on the scale of post-decision-making according to the teaching strategy, at 25.688, which is significant values at a level of 0.000, thus ensuring that the difference between the two study groups on the decision-making scale of dimensionality, according to the teaching strategy, is statistically significant. For identifying the difference in favor of any of the two groups, the modified arithmetic means, and standard errors were extracted for the achievement of the two study groups, as indicated in Table (13).

Table (13) Adjusted means and the standard errors of the two groups' performance in the decision-making scale (Teaching Method).

Group	N	Adjusted mean	Standard error
Experimental	17	66.64	2.82
Control	45	49.29	1.63

Table (13) shows that the experimental group taught using the flipped class strategy got an arithmetic mean of 66.64, while that of the control group taught by the traditional method was 49.29. This indicates that the difference was in favor of the mean of the experimental group, compared to the mean of the control group. This confirms the effectiveness of an educational environment based on the flipped classroom strategy in the decision-making scale of the class teacher students, and that the value of Eta-squared, which expresses the size of the effect this strategy had on the decision-making scale, is 0.303. This indicates that 30.3% of the difference in the decision-making scale is due to the flipped classroom teaching strategy, and the rest of the difference (69.7%) is due to other variables that the current study did not address.

• Is there a relationship between the acquisition of chemical concepts, scientific thinking, and the attitudes towards science (Scientific Literacy) among the classroom teacher students?

To answer the fifth question of the study, the correlation coefficients were calculated using the Pearson correlation coefficient between the test of acquiring chemical concepts, scientific thinking, and the trend towards science (scientific enlightenment) among the classroom teacher students, as indicated in the following table.

**Table (14)
Correlation coefficients using the Pearson correlation coefficient between the test of acquiring chemical concepts, scientific thinking, and the attitudes towards science (scientific literacy) among the classroom teacher students.**

Attitudes towards science	Scientific Thinking Test	
.805**	.822**	Test of chemical concepts
.000	.000	
.703**	Scientific Thinking Test	
.000		

Table (14) shows positive correlations and a statistical function between the test of acquiring chemical concepts and scientific thinking and the trend towards science (scientific literacy) among the classroom teacher students. The correlation coefficient between the test of chemical concepts and the test of scientific thinking reached 0.822, which is positive and significant at a significance level of 0.000. The correlation coefficient between the test of chemical concepts and the measure of attitude towards science was 0.805, which is positive and significant at the level of 0.000, while the correlation coefficient between the test of scientific thinking and the measure of attitude towards science was 0.703, which too is positive and significant at the level of 0.000.

• Discussing the results related to the question: Does the degree of acquisition of chemical concepts differ with a statistical significance at the level of $\alpha = 0.05$ among female classroom teacher students according to the teaching strategy used (flipped class/ traditional class)?

The results of the accompanying analysis of variance ANCOVA showed that there were statistically significant differences at the level of $\alpha = 0.05$ between the mean scores of students in the test of acquiring chemical concepts due to the method of teaching and in favor of the students who studied according to the flipped class, and the value of Eta squared, which expresses the size of the effect caused by this strategy in acquiring chemical concepts. The value is 0.842, indicating that 84.2% of the difference in acquiring chemical concepts is due to the teaching strategy of the flipped classroom. The researcher believes that this may be due to the flipped classroom being characterized by the characteristics such as providing an interactive environment that maintains the continuity of students' motivation to learn and their desire for continuous education, and achieving a link to theoretical information with practical situations that help learners to establish and preserve information. Additionally, the strategy's adoption of the element of modernity, as each part was presented in an unusual way for the students, attracted their attention and raised the level of their attainment. The flipped classroom focuses on educational goals and activities that achieve these goals, which made the students focus on them sufficiently, which was reflected in the level of their acquisition of chemical concepts positively. The researcher may attribute the result to the fact that the sum of experiences that the students experienced during learning made the application of learning a simple process. Students were also organized, as those in the experimental group had received knowledge in their homes before entering the educational platform through Microsoft Teams. This knowledge was simulated through activities and then emphasized through the lecture, active learning activities, and cooperative learning that allowed them to have fruitful discussions. This was in addition to the environment presented through flipped learning, containing exciting media for students and interaction with each other intentionally and as arranged for them by the teacher, which puts the students in a continuous learning process. This is in tune with the study of Al Hosani (2015) and Sharier (2017). This can be explained by the fact that the flipped class across the web makes education student-centered so that the student can see the chemical concepts before displaying them and view educational videos, which helps the student to deal with scientific knowledge and concepts in a scientific way that is more useful than memorizing this information. The flipped class method also allows the presentation of chemical concepts in a more practical and useful way than memorization, so that the chemical concepts were presented in a novel way, and the student's dollar was positive and active in obtaining the concept and browsing it while he was at home, in addition to obtaining the same information from more than one webpage, which clarifies and consolidates the concept for the student.

Discussing the results related to the question: Does the degree of development of scientific thinking skills differ with a statistical significance at the significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$ among the female classroom teacher students according to the teaching strategy used (flipped class/ traditional class)?

The accompanying analysis of variance (ANCOVA) shows that there were statistically significant differences at the level of $\alpha = 0.05$ between the averages of students' performance in the test of scientific thinking skills, and in favor of the experimental group. The value of Eta squared, which expresses the size of the effect that this strategy had on the development of scientific thinking skills is 0.669, and this shows that 66.9% of the difference in the development of scientific thinking skills is due to the flipped classroom teaching strategy. Hence, the flipped classroom strategy leads to the development of thinking and allows students to discuss, express opinions, justify positions, and state arguments, providing a real opportunity for students to express their opinion without embarrassment or fear, by arousing their interest and increasing their motivation to research through the diversity of sources for obtaining information before the actual lecture. The specific and carefully selected sources of information helped students behave like scientists by asking questions and answering them, and providing them with scientific thinking skills, as well as the creation of a positive collective learning environment in which the students participated in discussion and dialogue, and the practice of mental openness. This result agrees with that of Halili and Zainuddin (2016), who conducted a content analysis of twenty worksheets and research papers on the Flipped Learning Model, published between 2013 and 2015. Evidence was found of the positive effects of using the Flipped Learning Strategy on student achievement, motivation, thinking, participation, and class interaction.

Discussing the results related to the question: Does the degree of developing the attitude towards science differ with a statistical significance at the level of $\alpha = 0.05$ among the female classroom teacher students according to the teaching strategy used (flipped class/ traditional class)?

This result can be explained by the fact that the flipped classroom strategy leads to the development of thinking and allows students to discuss, express opinions, justify positions and mention arguments, providing a real opportunity for students to obtain the same scientific information from several scientific sources, thus increasing students' turnout, stimulating their motivation and turning them into scientists. The flipped classroom strategy also takes into account the individual differences between students, enabling them to express their opinion without embarrassment or fear by raising their interest and increasing their motivation to search for

appropriate solutions, adopting the behavior of scientists in discussing information, and creating a positive collective learning environment in which the students participate in discussion and dialogue. All this contributed to increasing the students' self-confidence, and their desire for more learning, research, and questioning to satisfy curiosity, and to practice open-mindedness, leading in turn to their acquisition of positive attitudes towards science.

This result was in tune with those of many studies that sought to verify the effect of the flipped classroom strategy on raising the level of motivation. Among these is a study whose results showed the positive impact of the flipped classroom strategy on the trend towards the subject in favor of the experimental group, and others (Johnson, 2012; 2013; Marlowe; 2012; Tuzun et al.), the results of which showed a positive effect of using the flipped classroom strategy in improving the level of motivation of the study sample. They also reflected the presence of positive trends for students who studied according to the flipped classroom strategy and that they enjoyed learning in this way, benefiting from watching lessons and activities in a flipped learning manner.

Discussion of the results related to the question

• Is there a relationship between the acquisition of chemical concepts, scientific thinking, and the trend towards science (scientific enlightenment) among the classroom teacher students?

Positive correlations and a statistical function were found between the test of acquiring chemical concepts, scientific thinking, and the trend towards science (scientific enlightenment) among the classroom teacher students, showing the importance of the flipped classroom strategy in developing Scientific Literacy among students.

Discussing the results related to the question: Does the degree of decision-making differ with a statistical significance at the level of $\alpha=0.05$ among female classroom teacher students according to the teaching strategy used (flipped class/ traditional class)?

This result is not because the flipped learning strategy has the advantage of students spending a large part of the time independently outside the classroom, leading them to self-regulate the learning process, rely on themselves in setting goals, planning, and monitoring, and resort to social assistance for understanding the educational material. Flipped Learning is an embodiment of student-centered education, consisting of watching videos at home, performing homework, trying to understand new and ambiguous concepts and topics included in the various videos, and working on taking notes about these clips, to be discussed the next day in the university lecture, contributes to directing the student to organize what he learns through planning, setting goals, and memorizing the educational material, which aids the development of decision-development skills. Students' individual differences, as they provide the opportunity for active participation of students, increase their enthusiasm and stimulate their motivation towards a company, generating a sense of responsibility and contributing to the development of their decision-making skills.

Recommendations and Suggestions

Considering the findings of the study, indicating a positive impact of teaching using the flipped classroom in Scientific Literacy and the development of decision-making skills, the following recommendations can be made:

- 1- The need to follow such methods in teaching chemistry that students can understand them in carrying out tasks and activities with the required speed, accuracy, and high motivation, and employing them in new situations to enhance the Scientific Literacy of students.
- 2- Not providing scientific solutions in chemistry to students in a ready-made manner, but rather, directing them to search for these solutions in a safe and stimulating learning environment for the development of scientific trends and the behavior of scientists.
- 3- Conducting more studies in the field of science with bigger samples and other stages of study.
- 4- Holding training courses for first-grade teachers and resource room teachers in the application of such modern approaches in science teaching.
- 5- Including the flipped classroom strategy for teaching science in the curricula and guides for science teachers
- 6- Conducting studies using the flipped class strategy on different samples and other skills.

Conclusion

These results may be attributed to the teaching strategy used, which led to a tangible improvement in the grades of students taught according to the flipped class preparation strategy, as it allows students to first view the content and gives them a pre-stimulus. There is also the additional availability of an attractiveness and suspense factor, reflected in their performance in the post-test. The improvement in students' results can also be explained by the flipped classroom strategy providing complete freedom for students to choose the appropriate

time and speed at which they learn, and the possibility of keeping the study material sent to them through various technological tools and reviewing it repeatedly. All these bridge the knowledge gap, which is supplemented by the immediate feedback provided to them by the teacher during the lecture. Thus, the application of the flipped classroom strategy had a clear impact in helping students improve their performance and overcome some of the problems they face, as confirmed by various studies (Khalil, 2015; Al-Kahili, 2014) indicating an increase in the rate of interaction among students, an increase in the desire to engage in activities, the occurrence of learning by a large percentage, the development of self-confidence and the ability for dialogue, and a high degree of awareness of the importance of time management. This result also agreed with those of Marlowe (2012) and Tuzun (2009).

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